

A Rhetorical Analysis of a Daily Editorial: 'Wishing Iraq Well'

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ABSTRACT: The present study is an attempt to identify the rhetorical pattern and rhetorical devices that exist in an English editorial titled *Wishing Iraq well*. This editorial was published on December 19, 2011 in the New Straits Times (NST) –the oldest English daily tabloid newspaper- in Malaysia. The theoretical framework of this analysis is based on the Systemic Functional (SF) theory of language and genre (Halliday & Hasan, 1989) which proposes a generic pattern namely generic structural potential (GSP) of text development for editorials. The data of the study were culled from the website of the newspaper: <http://www.nst.com.my/opinion/editorial/wishing-iraq>. The aim of the study is to identify the elements of generic structural potential (GSP), their sequence, and some rhetorical figures used throughout the editorial text. The findings revealed eight rhetorically structural elements which include Run-on Headline (RH), Addressing an Issue (AI), Providing Background Information (BI), Initiation of Argumentation (IA), Argumentation (A), Concluding Remarks (CR), Articulating a position (AP), and Articulating a Solution (AS). A number of rhetorical organizational devices/figures such as zeugma, altercasting, metonymy, alliteration, personality, parataxis, antithesis, etc. were discovered as devices of influencing and persuading readers. Sequence wise, the following GSP was explored and formulated: RH^{AI}(BI)^{IA}A^{CR}(AP)^{AS}

Keywords: rhetorical figures; rhetorical structure; Generic Structural potential (GSP); daily editorial; zeugma; metonymy.

1. INTRODUCTION

Writing and rhetoric have recently revisited. These two factors might combine and cause persuasive written texts. Rhetoric manifests itself in patterns; employs devices to help audiences better realize and accept the main intent of writers. This realization may lead to crystallized text comprehension for readers and a more effectively persuasive piece of text for authors. It is deemed that rhetorical structure and devices/strategies influence the English writing (Ferris 1994). The roles of these rhetorical structure and devices on how writers organize, develop, and present their written texts are inevitable.

As Kaplan (1966, p.20) stresses, Anglo-European expository essays follow a linear development while written texts in oriental languages such as Malay, Persian, Chinese, and Japanese make use of a spiral way of presenting ideas as to delay the main idea to the end of the text. It seems that rhetoric has a lot to do with the way ideas are presented and persuaded.

According to Kaplan (2001) rhetorical patterns of languages are different from one language to another. Apart from general English proficiency which includes the mastery of skills and sub-skills, it seems that some other factors might involve the way each of the above nationals i.e. the oriental languages' speakers, write. These geared factors could be some rhetorical devices or figures, and (maybe) their background transfers from their first language or the context where English comes from.

1.1 Statement of the problem

The purpose of this research is dual. On one hand, it attempts to identify the rhetorical structure (GSP) and on the other hand, it endeavors to find out as well as examine the rhetorical devices used in a English editorial published in a Malaysian paper namely *the New Strait Times*.

This study seems worth an investigation because firstly, the rhetoric of newspaper editorials as a representative of media discourse has hardly yet been studied in Malaysia and therefore this sub-genre seems neglected in this respect as observed by the current researcher of the study and reflected in the literature review. Secondly the preliminary studies carried out by the present researcher have revealed that the art of rhetoric which is today a sub-category of applied linguistics could exert varied functions in press editorials which are argumentative and persuasive in nature. Traces of rhetorical structure, devices or figures have been found functioning in editorial texts, yet rhetorical explanations and descriptions of press editorial sub-genre is conspicuous by its absence.

Hence, based on the direct observation of student writing texts and preliminary (pilot study) editorial analyses, it has been decided to make an investigation on the above observation and Kaplan's famous thought patterns by embarking on this rhetorical study. Hence this investigation tries to find out the rhetorical structure (GSP) used in a Malaysian-written English editorial in line with what Kaplan (1996) calls '(spiral) oriental languages'. In part, the study is an endeavor to find out on rhetorical devices/figures employed in newspaper editorial of *the New Strait Times* paper. In whole, this small-in-scope investigation tries to realize how a Malaysian editorial writer of English rhetorically develop a newspaper editorial to impact their audiences.

1.2 Research Questions

Since the study revolves around rhetorical structure (GSP) and rhetorical devices, the following research questions have been designed:

1. What rhetorical structure (GSP) is used by the Malaysian-written English editorial?
2. What are the rhetorical devices that the Malaysian writer of English editorial use? How are these devices distributed in the editorial text?

1.3 Significance of the Study

The study attempts to make the following significant contributions:

1.3.1 Contributions to the Genre of Media

Editorials seem a neglected sub-genre with too limited literature in some countries. Studies like the present one could be an initiative to popularize as well as help to understand the genre of media in general and editorial sub-genre in particular among the public. This negligence which has brought about the title of 'Cinderella' genre for editorials is more obvious in some nations as there are so limited studies carried out on newspaper editorials. The current study may be able to encourage more researchers to find as well as fill out the gaps in this (sub) genre which will lead to its growth and improvement.

1.3.2 Contributions to Pedagogy

The type of rhetorical structure and rhetorical devices and their influence concluded from this study will hopefully be presented in an ESL conference or reflected in a cited linguistic journal. The outcomes of the study may be integrated into the English writing skill syllabi or modules (at least) in Malaysia.

Besides, it should be noted that what students are explicitly taught about writing in a second language is central in the investigation of their writing choices. Thus curriculum professionals should wise up in whether or not, what and how much rhetoric inclusion or exclusion to make in order to enrich curriculums and writing skill as well. Editorial writing could become a writing genre in institutional curriculums in order to teach students a) how to write (use linguistics as a science) and b) how to persuade others effectively (use rhetoric as an art). Once students learn rhetoric, its functions, and influence on writing, they involuntarily grow conscious of the persuasive purposes that authors reserve for them. Later on, they better develop their critical thinking skills and rhetorical resistance to not say YES easily to an argumentative written discourse.

Lastly, Leki (1992) highlights that it is of importance to help students be '[culturally and rhetorically] informed' in their writing choices. Studies on rhetoric, can result in 'instant enlightenment' when students grow mindful of

their inherent assumptions underlying their L1 and L2 writing conventions.

1.3.3 Contributions to Research and Methodology

There are many rhetorical studies that have applied one of the Swale's models -such as the Move model- for editorial analysis. Following a handful of studies, the current investigation, instead uses the GSP model of the SFL theory to analyze editorials. The use of this almost novel analytic tool (GSP) could give rise to its own popularization and application among researchers not only in analyzing media genre but in other genres like writing which encompasses business letters, reports, research articles, etc. Furthermore, in some nations including Malaysia, the discourse (sub) genre of press editorials, have rarely been analyzed in a systematically explicit way therefore the current research might serve as a stepping stone to more research studies that tend to cover varied rhetorical perspectives. Last but not the least is that studies of newspaper editorials as they are the best selected examples of persuasive writing might become increasingly generalizable (Connor 1996). It is therefore hoped that the current investigation's findings will be publicized and generalized as well. The researcher is optimistic that the GSP model would suit the present rhetorical study as well as the other futuristic ones; therefore the model may be caught on among other researchers and rhetoricians as well.

1.3.4 Contributions to Society and Language

The findings of the investigation will hopefully shed light on the importance of rhetoric as an art as well as applied linguistics branch. Some factors that involve the way Malaysians write and persuade will be open to people. The results would contribute to bridging communication breakdown and enriching the quality of understanding. This boosted understanding could be responsive to the lately emphasis and attention paid by the Malaysia's ministry of higher education, Dato Seri Mohamed Khaled Nordin, as he repeatedly stressed the importance of acquiring Bahasa Malaya (Malaysian lingua franca) and its culture for international students and signed recent MOUs with some middle-eastern counties with the intention of bringing in more international students to Malaysia. Also last year, the same ministry, mandated the public universities to conduct mandatory Bahasa Malaya related courses for all international students in Malaysia a) to increase contextual awareness, b) avoid/reduce misunderstanding and misinterpretation that may erupt in casualties as it did yet, and c) to ease communication between Malaysians and foreigners which will bring in (economical) prosperity to the fast-developing Malaysia as an educational excellence. Hence, the outcome of studies like the present one will crystallize a better image of Malaysia, its nation, the way its people write and persuade (here of course, in a small scope). Knowing people's rhetoric (writing rhetoric for instance) is equal to knowing how to persuade them.

Raising the knowledge level of people about rhetorical understanding in general and newspaper editorial rhetoric in particular seems crucial. The part that newspaper editorials play in persuading as well as shaping (or changing) the public opinion is inevitable. Broadening editorial readers' minds with some findings regarding the rhetorical structure and devices of editorial texts may be beneficial in helping readers ponder a little bit rather than being quickly persuaded. Audiences will better recognize rhetorical devices and figure out their role in influencing the rhetoric of written or verbal discourse. Hopefully, they won't easily accept an argued claim and might instead look into it with the use of rhetorical knowledge.

In addition, press editorials as an un-researched area in some nations such as Malaysia could receive the attention it deserves. The newspaper editorial (sub) genre might then be able to grow and create careers in future for ambitious writers and turns into an industry.

Unlike the contrastive rhetorical studies done before which used native versus non-native English language dichotomy, the current study tends to center on the English language used in Malaysia. This study aims to a) give rise to the non-native Englishes, b) show how context and rhetoric might influence the way authors write (here editorials), c) to highlight that native-English language is a means (for communication) rather than an end and therefore needless to be used as yardstick for comparison and verification. d) to encourage more in-depth research on non-native Englishes such as the one used in Malaysia e) to enforce decentralization and independence from what a western language might bring along such as contextual/cultural values or devalues, habits, etc.

1.4 Theoretical Framework

Introduced by Halliday and Hassan (1989), the concept of Generic Structure Potential (GSP) is designed for any specific contextual configuration (context) to define a genre (pp. 63-65). The GSP model which is driven from the Systemic Functional Theory is a compact statement that shows the elements and their sequence in the structure of a text. These macro-structural elements, irregardless of their size hold the potential or possibility for a text structure or *unity of structure* (macro connexity). The sequenced elements that make up the GSP of a genre, offer at least a proposition.

The GSP model has been employed to analyze casual conversation (Ventola 1979), Gossip (Slade 1994), service encounters (Halliday and Hassan 1985, Ventola 1987, Togher & et al), and daily editorials (Babaei 2010, Ansary and babaei 2004, and Shokouhi and Amin 2010). Several other researchers such as Mitchell (1975) who identified the GSP of the genre of *Shop Transaction* in Libya, Ghadessy (1993) who established the GSP of *Business Letters*, Hasan (1984) and Paltridge (1993) who investigated the rhetorical structure of the Introduction sections of RAs, and lastly Henry and Roseberry (1997) who identified the GSP of introductions and endings of

forty essays, applied the theoretical model of the GSP successfully.

Halliday and Hassan (1989) in an attempt to explain the GSP of the "Service Encounter" (or shop transaction) examined a shop transaction text between a customer and shop assistant. They (1989, p 62) believe that any shop transaction is composed of a set of optional and obligatory macro-structural elements ordered specifically. They eventually came out with the following GSP which consists of the elements of Greeting (G), Sale Initiation (SI), Sale Enquiry (SE), Sale Request (SR), Sale Compliance (SC), Sale (S), Purchase (P), Purchase Closure (PC), and Finish (F).

[(G).(SI)^][(SE.){SR^SC^}^S^] P^PC(^F)

Halliday (1990, p. 34) maintains that the GSP model of the SFL is particularly suitable for any investigatory study that that enables us to analyse any passage and relate it to its context in the discourse, and also to the general background of the text: who it is written for, what is its angle on the subject matter and so on.

Applying the Generic Structure Potential (GSP) model, Babaie (2010) described the rhetorical patterns of English newspaper editorials as an important public genre. Based on the same model adopted from the Systemic Functional (SF) theory of language and genre (see Halliday & Hasan, 1989), Babaie identified four *obligatory* structural elements (Run-on Headline, Addressing an Issue, Argumentation, and Articulating a Position) which existed in 90% of the sampled editorials. These elements were sequenced as: RH^AI^A^AP. In addition, came up a few *optional* elements which are: providing Background Information (BI), which either preceded AI or followed it, Initiation of Argumentation (IA), and Closure of Argumentation (CA). These optional elements of the GSP, in some cases, were helpful to writers to start off their arguments, and sometimes used to finely round off the arguments. This study delved into the GSP of the English editorials. Babaie (2010) contrasted the editorials written by Americans and Iranians.

In another study to find out the distinctive rhetorical features of English newspaper editorials, Ansary and Babaii (2004) made use of the GSP model of the Hallidayian approach to identify a generic pattern of text development for editorials. They culled 30 editorials from 'Washington Times' which represent the American newspaper. Four obligatory elements (Run-on Headline, Addressing an Issue, Argumentation, and Articulating a Position) appeared in the 90% of the sampled editorials. A few optional elements in the same editorials were explored to provide Background Information (BI), Initiation of Argumentation (IA), and Closure of Argumentation (CA) which sometimes used to round off the arguments. Ansari & Babaie (2004) used the GSP model in the study. Their work showed that just identification of rhetorical structure of American editorials was under investigation.

Thus the present study aims to apply the GSP of English newspaper editorials as a theoretical model to investigate the rhetorical patterns, devices, and persuasive strategies.

2. Literature Review

As defined by Valero-garces (1996:281), rhetoric is “the strategies the writer uses to convince readers of his/her claims and to increase the credibility of his/her research.” Rhetoric is of two major trends which maintain the term rhetoric in their designations: generative rhetoric which was developed under the influence of Neom Chomsky and the other is contrastive rhetoric (Malmkjaer 2004). It is seen that rhetoric, in effect, might need certain devices to become more empowered. Such devices are called rhetorical devices or figures.

A rhetorical device/figure is an artful deviation (Corbett, 1990). In fact this artful act occurs when an expression and its expectation deviate. As a result, the expression looks rejected and not to the point. The deviation follows an invariant template across a variety of context and content (McQuarrie & Mick, 1996). In other words, rhetorical devices are devices or strategies used by authors to attain specific rhetorical goals. These devices include rhetorical questions, paradox, anaphora, metonymy, personification, irony, to name but a few. Understanding the meaning of rhetorical devices is absolutely important as it leads readers to determining the author’s rhetorical intent which in turn yields the fruit of realizing the meaning and/or effect of a written text. These devices demonstrate themselves as powerful tools of persuasion throughout written texts one of which is newspaper editorials.

A newspaper editorial is generally defined as “an article in a newspaper that gives the opinion of the editor or publisher on a topic or item of news” (Sinclair, 1995). Newspaper editorial articles are generally regarded as the large class of opinion discourse which is considered a newspaper sub-genre these days (van Dijk, 2005). Regarded as a discourse (sub) genre, newspaper editorials have sparingly been analyzed in a systematic and explicit way. The structure of editorials is different from that of the news reports they refer to (Van Dijk, 1988a). Their limited length is between 200 and 500 words and they are located at a fix place in the newspaper. In terms of topic, they revolve around cultural, health, socio-political, economic, education and some other issues. Editorials more or less have been a subject of investigation by several researchers.

Katajamaki and Koskelain (2007), in a rhetorical investigation, studied the structure of editorials in English, Swedish and Finnish business newspapers: *Financial Times*, *Dagens Industri*, and *Taloussanommat*. The study revolved around the following inquiries: a typical rhetorical structure, its types, the factors involved in the content, language, and culture. The material of the study consisted of 22 editorials from these three business newspapers. As a starting point for their analysis, they used a modification of Van Dijk’s (1995) view of the rhetorical structure of editorials as a model for the study. Van Dijk (1995) quoted in Katajamaki and Koskelain (2007: 2) classifies editorials into three sections. For each section, there are specific stages and functions. Although the editorial texts represented three countries and their three languages, the

variation in the rhetorical structure was of subtle variation. This work (Katajamaki and Koskelain, 2007) used a different model - Van Dijk’s (1995) view of the rhetorical structure of editorials- for analysis. This study is a contrastive rhetoric to identify and distinguish the rhetorical patterns used in English, Swedish, and Finish newspaper editorials.

In an attempt to investigate the rhetorical elements in editorials, Shokouhi and Amin (2010) sampled sixty newspaper editorials culled from six newspapers; New York Times, Washington Times (written in English by native speakers of English), Tehran Times, Keyhan International written (written in English by non-native English speakers), and Keyhan, and Resalat (written in Persian by native speakers of Persian). They also administered four reading comprehension tests to 27 university students. The study resulted in the point that the generic structure includes three obligatory elements in almost all editorials. These three elements of the GSP were similar regardless of the language and place of publication. Also based on the result of the reading comprehension tests, it was made clear that the differences between students’ performance on the test was linked to the varied degree of their familiarity with the content and context rather than the text structure. The study (Shokouhi & Amin, 2010) applied triangulation. Using the GSP model, this rigorous study on one hand compared and contrasted English editorials written in Iranian and US newspapers and on the other hand between English and Persian editorials written by Iranians. In addition, Shokouhi and Amin (2010) involved (twenty-seven) student readers of editorials through reading comprehension tests. It is a wonder why reading comprehension of the editorial readers rather than the degree of reader’s acceptance, rejection, influence, or persuasion – that might be caused by editorial argumentation- was measured. It is a commonsense that the main purpose behind arguing some claims through editorials is to have readers digest and agree with the claimed points. According to Conner (2001), “in most newspapers, the purpose of editorials is to influence the opinion of readers on some controversial issue” (p. 143). Reading comprehension plays an important part in reader’s trying to understand the argument though. Understanding the debated problems (means) seems just to serve as to transport the reader toward persuasion and support (end). In other words, in this study, attempts were made to a) spot the rhetorical patterns of editorials, b) identify their differences, and c) test reader’s comprehension of editorials. Therefore, the reasons why these rhetorical patterns emerged as well as whether or not the editorials succeeded to perform their major tasks – to win influence, persuasion, and support- are absent in Babaie & Amin’s work.

As to the rhetorical devices, Gale & Anmarie (1999) investigated the use of rhetorical devices in advertisements. Compared to those adverts without rhetorical devices, adverts that contain rhetorical devices proved more effective compared to those that do not. Advertisements that make use of rhetorical devices showed superior recall

and superior persuasion. They also revealed that one of the most effective persuasive methods is rhetorical devices/figures. The outcome of the study revealed 96 percent agreement.

In a nutshell, the above literature has revolved around faucets of rhetoric that knit a newspaper editorial. Hence, it is obvious that rare studies have been yet carried out to center on the English editorials written by Malaysians. The current study tries to fill up the gap in there to some extent. It tends to deviate from in-depth reference to the L1 (Malay). Nor does pinpoint to the difficulties with which editorial writers are faced with, if any. Instead, rhetorical structure and devices of an English editorial written published in *the New Strait Times* will make the focal areas of the investigation.

Thus, a study that concentrates on these three faucets: a) identification of rhetorical structure (GSP) in editorials and b) identification of rhetorical devices in newspaper editorial writing are deemed contributively new to the domains of rhetorical research and press editorial sub-genre in Malaysia.

3. METHODOLOGY Material and Procedure

The Generic Structure Potential (GSP) model which is adopted from the SFL theory of Halliday and Hassan (1989) has been considered to be used for the study. Using this model, first the editorial text is read and segmented into some meta-text elements. These elements later are scrutinized in order to locate the rhetorical devices in them. Next, the sequence of such rhetorically structural elements would be presented. In addition, the researcher has looked into the editorial text to find out rhetorical organizational figures as well as their count and frequencies and locations where they are most and least accumulated using text analysis of the data.

The data of the study has been obtained from an English editorial text titled *Wishing Iraq Well*. This editorial has been written by a Malaysian writer (whose name is not mentioned in the editorial) using the English language. The editorial was published on December 19, 2011 in the *new Straits Times* (the NST), a well-read Malaysian newspaper. The digital data has been culled from the website of the

above-said newspaper: <http://www.thenst.com.my/opinion/editorial/wishing-iraq-well>. The NST is regarded as the well-read and oldest daily paper in Malaysia. It has the circulation of 200,000 copies a day. This tabloid-sized daily paper first operated in 1845 and now is published in print as well as online formats.

4. ANALYSIS

The analysis of the editorial text initiates from the text analysis of rhetorical structure (GSP). Accordingly after studying the editorial text, eight potential elements which include Run-on Headline (RH), Articulating an Issue (AI), Providing Background Information (BI), Initiation of Argumentation (IA), Argumentation (A), Concluding Remark (CR), Articulating a Position (AP), and Articulating a Solution (AS) appeared to construct the GSP of the editorial in question. In terms of size, BI (138 words) and IA (120 words) were the largest while RH (3) and CR (13) proved the smallest elements in the GSP. Therefore, the following rhetorical structure (GSP) of the editorial has been schemed as below:

RH^AI^(BI)^(IA)^A^(CR)^(AP)^(AS)

In the above GSP, the round brackets are indicative of element optionality. It means that whether or not a bracket-enclosed element appear in the GSP is not vitally important. The existence of optional elements may add to power the persuasion, effectiveness and completion of the editorial claim though. Halliday and Hasan maintains that the appearance of these elements [GSP obligatory and optional elements] in a specific order corresponds to our perception of whether the text is complete or incomplete (1989: 62). Hence, BI, IA, CR, AP, AS are all optional whereas RH, AI, and A proved obligatory. The sequence in the above GSP is shown by the caret sign (^). Violation of the sequence among the GSP elements should not be violated as it might result in disorganization of ideas and presentation.

The following table illustrates the GSP element more vividly:

Table 1 – The Elements Rhetorical Structure (GSP)

No.	GSP element	Element content	Word Count
1	RH	Wishing Iraq well	3
2	AI	JUST days before the invasion in March 2003, 58 percent of Americans supported sending troops into Iraq.	17
3	BI	There was also euphoria in the streets of Baghdad when American bombs lit up the sky like Christmas and American soldiers tore down a statue of Saddam Hussein. But it did not take long before angry crowds of Iraqis demanded that the "liberators" go home. Though it took a little bit longer, once it became clear that the war in Iraq could not be considered "mission accomplished", as proclaimed by United States president George W. Bush on May 1, 2003, the US-led occupation also became increasingly unpopular among Americans. However, even with the election in 2008 of a new president who had opposed what he called the "wrong war" when he was running for office and pledged an early	138

		withdrawal from Iraq, the US flag was lowered in Baghdad only on Thursday, almost nine years after the invasion.	
4	IA	Nearly 4,500 US soldiers have died, more than 32,000 wounded, and US\$800 billion (RM2.48 trillion) authorised by the US Congress for fighting the war in Iraq. As there is no official body count, an accurate death toll of Iraqis will never be known, but estimates range from 100,000 to one million lives lost, and as many as 3.5 million displaced. According to a recent Pew report, only 44 per cent of returning American war veterans said the Iraq war was worth it. However, US Defence Secretary Leon Panetta has said the costs and casualties in Iraq had not been in vain because the mission of "making that country sovereign and independent and able to govern and secure itself" had been achieved.	120
5	A	While it is legitimate to say that not only has the war cost Iraq more than it has been worth, but also that a war that was invented to get rid of bogus weapons of mass destruction should never have (A) been allowed to get past first base in the first place.	52
6	CR	...all this is water under the bridge now. The past cannot be undone	13
7	AP	Now that the last American soldiers have left Iraq, the US should leave the Iraqis to resolve their own problems.	20
8	AS	The hope is that the Iraqis will be able to reconcile their differences and build a better future.	18

Table 2- Total distribution of rhetorical devices

(Excerpt) No.	GSP Element	RD(s) used	No of RD(s)	RD Frequency	RD Instance
1	RH	Metonymy	1	1	Iraq
2	AI	Alliterations	1	2	...supported sending and into Iraq...
3	BI	Simile, antithesis, irony, analogy	4	1	Simile(sky),antithesis(however), irony(libertators),analogy(presidents' says)
4	IA	Zeugma, parataxis, alliteration, & altercasting	4	1	Zeugma(,and),parataxis(), alliteration(lives lost), & altercasting()
5	A	Zeugma, parallelism, altercasting, personality - authoritarian vs. communicative-	4	1	Zeugma, parallelism(first base, first place),altercasting(rational-directed villain), personality- authoritarian vs. communicative- (hammer and anvil)
6	CR	Metaphor	1	1	Metaphor(water is likened to past deeds)
7	AP	Metonymy	1	1	...the US
8	AS	Zeugma	1	1	...differences and build...
Total	8	-	17	9	-

As to the rhetorical devices/ figures, many have been found in the structure. These discovered devices include zeugma, alliteration, metonymy, altercasting, simile, antithesis, irony, analysis, parataxis, parallelism, metaphor, and personality. The rhetorical devices were located more or less in all GSP elements. It was made clear that BI, IA, and A were the elements that accommodate as many as four rhetorical devices in them probably due to their large size.

Table two demonstrates the total distribution of the rhetorical elements throughout the editorial text.

As stated before, twelve rhetorical devices have been explored. These devices were already ordered in table three in terms of how frequent they have been throughout the editorial article. Table three could better show the name and frequency of the rhetorical devices:

Table 3 – Frequency distribution of Rhetorical Devices (RD)

No.	RD	RD frequency	GSP element(s)	Frequency Ranking
1	Zeugma	3	IA,A,AS	1
2	Alliteration	3	AI,AI,IA	1
3	Metonymy	2	RH,AP	2

4	Altercasting	2	IA,A	2
5	Simile	1	BI	3
6	Antithesis	1	BI	3
7	Irony	1	BI	3
8	Analogy	1	BI	3
9	Parataxis	1	IA	3
10	Parallelism	1	A	3
11	Metaphor	1	CR	3
12	Personality	1	A	3

5. CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

Findings of the present paper clearly demonstrate that there existed seven rhetorical elements in the structure of the editorial text: Run-on Headline (RH), Addressing an Issue (AI), Argumentation (A), Providing Background Information (BI), Initiation of Argumentation (IA), Concluding Remarks (CR), Articulating a Position (AP), and Articulating a Solution (AS). Therefore, (RH), (AI), and (A) are obligatory since their existence in the text is really inevitably essential while (BI), (IA), (CR), (AP), and (AS) are considered optional elements whose presence just better complete and empower the argumentation in the GSP (Halliday and Hasan, 1989). Sequence wise, the following GSP was formulated which could serve an answer to research question one of the study which is concerned with the rhetorical structure (GSP) of the editorial article under investigation:

RH^AI^(BI)^(IA)^A^(CR)^(AP)^(AS)

As shown earlier in the analysis section, the text was analyzed based on the rhetorical structure model (GSP) of the editorials as a sub-genre of the newspaper genre and rhetorical figures. Following Halliday and Hasan (1989), Ghadessy (1993), Paltridge (1993) Henry and Roseberry (1997), Ansary (2004), Ansary and Babaii (2004) and Hodges (2006) who have adopted the GSP model, this study has identified the same rhetorical elements mentioned above. The only difference found between the GSP explored by previous works cited above and that of the current paper is the sequence of the last three elements – (CR)-(AP)-(AS) positions. In the other words, (CR) precedes (AP) and (AS) in the GSP of the present study whereas in the GSP of the previous works cited above, (CR) is preceded by (AS).

To respond to research question two which revolves around the rhetorical devices, twelve rhetorical devices/figures have been discovered across the editorial text GSP elements. Zeugma, alliteration were among the most frequent devices each appearing in three GSP elements.

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Appendix I

19 December 2011 | Last updated at 01:07AM

Wishing Iraq well

JUST days before the invasion in March 2003, 58 per cent of Americans supported sending troops into Iraq.(AI)

There was also euphoria in the streets of Baghdad when American bombs lit up the sky like Christmas and American soldiers tore down a statue of Saddam Hussein. But it did not take long before angry crowds of Iraqis demanded that the "liberators" go home. Though it took a little bit longer, once it became clear that the war in Iraq could not be considered "mission accomplished", as proclaimed by United States president George W. Bush on May 1, 2003, the US-led occupation also became increasingly unpopular among Americans. However, even with the election in 2008 of a new president who had opposed what he called the "wrong war" when he was running for office and pledged an early withdrawal from

Iraq, the US flag was lowered in Baghdad only on Thursday, almost nine years after the invasion.

Nearly 4,500 US soldiers have died, more than 32,000 wounded, and US\$800 billion (RM2.48 trillion) authorised by the US Congress for fighting the war in Iraq. As there is no official body count, an accurate death toll of Iraqis will never be known, but estimates range from 100,000 to one million lives lost, and as many as 3.5 million displaced. According to a recent Pew report, only 44 per cent of returning American war veterans said the Iraq war was worth it. However, US Defence Secretary Leon Panetta has said the costs and casualties in Iraq had not been in vain because the mission of "making that country sovereign and independent and able to govern and secure itself" had been achieved.

While it is legitimate to say that not only has the war cost Iraq more than it has been worth, but also that a war that was invented to get rid of bogus weapons of mass destruction should never have (been allowed to get past first base in the first place, all this is water under the bridge now. The past cannot be undone. Now that the last American soldiers have left Iraq, the US should leave the Iraqis to resolve their own problems. The hope is that the Iraqis will be able to reconcile their differences and build a better future.

Read more: [Wishing Iraq well - Editorial - New Straits Times](http://www.nst.com.my/opinion/editorial/wishing-iraq-well-1.21326#ixzz1h5cMwQrj) <http://www.nst.com.my/opinion/editorial/wishing-iraq-well-1.21326#ixzz1h5cMwQrj>

AUTOBIOGRAPHY

Hassan Fartousi, an academician and researcher, is working toward a doctorate in the English Language and Applied Linguistics at the University of Malaya – based in Malaysia. As well as Malaysia, He holds 16 years of experience in the English language teaching in the UAE and Iran. Hassan has published and presented papers in Semantics, having a master of TESL from the IIU, a public university in Malaysia. His areas of interest include Rhetoric, writing skill, Semantics, and ELT.